

The Role of Happiness on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance: A Cross-Cultural Research in Italy and Turkey*

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Abstract

The research aims to analyze the explanatory effects of workplace happiness on employee performance and discover whether the variables were affected by cultural variations. The Italian sample, taken in July 2017 consisting of 409 responses resulted that "happiness at work" positively affects employee performance, fully mediates between job satisfaction and performance. Besides, job satisfaction indirectly associates performance only through the developer contribution of "happiness at work". The Turkish sample, taken in January 2018 consisting of 550 responses showed the positive effect of "happiness at work" on employee performance, moderates only by the means of the interaction of job satisfaction and performance. The study provides current validation for the assumption that "Happy employees are more productive at work" and contributes to previous studies suggesting that relationships of variables can be affected by cultural characteristics.

Key words: Job Satisfaction, Happiness at Work, Employee Performance, Cross-Cultural Comparison

JEL Code: J28, I31, M16

1. Introduction

Work attitudes are effective a significant factor in choosing work-related behaviors. In this context, job satisfaction has always been seen to be central since it was investigated in the literature and has been associated with different result parameters.

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As Ozer (2008) emphasized, the results of the Hawthorne Researchers in the 1930s drew attention to the effects of employees' attitudes on performance, in response to the question "Is a happy employee an efficient employee?". However, the relationships between job satisfaction and performance are controversial. Happiness is defined in the glossary as "Pride felt being able to reach all the aspirations in a complete and continuous manner: prosperity, well-being, eudaimonia, bliss and felicity" (Turkish Language Association Dictionary, n.d.). Researchers describe happiness in general as follows: "Happiness is a function of the harmony between events and circumstances in the individual's surroundings and the established tendencies and behaviors within" (Fisher, 2010b, p. 394). Besides this function, happiness is likely to be redesigned with deliberately chosen voluntary behavior(s) as Fisher (2010b) pointed out. Preliminary study held on well-being at an organizational level, asks employees whether they feel good or bad when they are doing their job at work. It was found that those events which cause good feelings and bad feelings are independent (Herzberg et al., 1959). In the following studies, it was observed that events that cause positive feelings increase the motivation of the employees and quality, but also reduce layoffs (Lawler, 1992; Pfeffer, 1998).

The contemporary employer-employee relationship is increasingly based on a mutual exchange of interests in meeting their respective expectations of each other (Roehling et al., 2001). Accordingly, the importance of encouraging employees to attain both job satisfaction and better performance has considerably increased. Moreover, being happy is also one of the most valuable and important objectives of everybody. Fisher (2010a:48), however, has asserted that "previous studies have not been able to adequately illuminate the link between job satisfaction and performance because the mediating role played by attitudes and feelings about employee happiness have been ignored". As Fisher (2010b) pointed out, there has not been adequate research in the social sciences about the "Happiness at work" variable, while subjects studied extensively such as job satisfaction and performance are generally not tested with an intermediate variable. Therefore, this research will be one of the pioneering studies in the literature that uses the "happiness at work" parameter as an intermediate variable. The findings to be obtained from surveys conducted in Italy and Turkey, assess the effect of relationships between variables in shaping the cultural context, and show the contribution of "happiness at work" to business practices in different cultures.

The problematic of this study is "are happy employees more efficient?". The study seeks an answer to this question by researching the role of happiness in terms of the effect of job satisfaction on performance. For this reason, the following literature review was conducted to discover, understand, and analyze the said variables.

Job Satisfaction is an attitude that explains how the individual feels about different aspects of his job and reveals how much the individual likes his/her job (satisfaction) or dislikes it (dissatisfaction) (Spector, 1997). Job satisfaction is

defined, in general, as the emotional response of employees to the work they do during their working life, the company they work for, their work environment and the experiences they gain through employment. Descriptions can be classified as follows: a) as per one's expectations from the job b) evaluation of job qualifications c) general attitude towards work.

Lawler (1973) defines it as, the relationship between the employee's expectations from the job and what the job offers to him/her. Gibson, Ivancevich, Donnelly and Konopaske (2012) states that job satisfaction occurs when the characteristics of the job (necessity, job variety, job description, feedback, friendship relations) match the employee's wishes. People join organizations for specific purposes to realize their expectations. According to the traditional perspective job satisfaction, which explains all the feelings an individual has towards his/her job, is not only based on the characteristics of the job, but also is shaped by the individual's expectations of the job (Lu et al, 2005). Employees demonstrate an attitude towards to their jobs. Job satisfaction is a general result of the attitudes relates to the physical and mental well-being of the employee (Asik, 2010).

According to a definition “happiness” is an emotion of joy, gladness, satisfaction, and well-being (American Psychological Association, n.d.). Happiness has always attracted the attention of philosophers. However, it has only recently come to the fore in psychological research. Prior to the rise of positive psychology in the last decade by Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi (2000), studies have focused disproportionately on disease-modelled depression, stress, and similar negative experiences and outcomes rather than exploring happiness and other positive variables. Happiness is classified “as hedonic and eudemonic” (Fisher, 2010b). While feeling of and orientation to pleasure explain hedonic happiness, eudemonic happiness refers to the adaptation to conditions of the outside world which can achieve inner harmony. As shown in Figure 1, Diener (2000) treats happiness as the life satisfaction obtained from positive emotions accompanying well-being. According to Diener (1984) “dimensions related to the hedonic concept of happiness are positive feelings, negative feelings and well-being” (p.543). Well-being is the frequency of recurrence of positive emotions and situations provided by personal satisfaction from life. While subjective well-being stems from enjoying personal experiences, psychological well-being stems from personal potential and success (self-acceptance, positive social relationships, gaining independence, environmental control, and personal development (Keyes, Shmotkin and Ryff, 2002; Deci and Ryan, 2008).

2. Literature Review

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Figure 1. Classification of Happiness

Source: Fisher, C. D. (2010). "Happiness at Work", ePublications@bond, Queensland.

Seligman (2002) and Warr (2007) (see Figure 1). Job-related happiness models are heavily grounded on hedonic experiences classified in Figure 1. Fisher (2010b: 385) defines: "job satisfaction, emotional commitment, positive belief and the experience of positive affects during work". Since Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi (2000) laid the foundations of positive psychology, the examination of happiness and other positive attitudes as opposed to dominant and disease-oriented psychology has gained importance in psychology. This was subsequently followed by Fineman (2006) and Roberts (2006) studies, happiness and cultural positive relations are discussed in the context of organizational life

change. Moreover, Luthans and Avolio's (2009) study addresses positive organizational behavior in the context of thesis-antithesis. The questioning of the concept of happiness in the field of organizational behavior in terms of positive organizational work was undertaken by Cameron et al. (2003) currently addresses questions of happiness in the field of positive organizational behavior. Luthans (2002) and Wright (2003) have asked the following:

1. How is happiness defined and measured?
2. What are the antecedents of happiness?
3. What are the consequences of happiness? (Fisher, 2010b: 384).

It is possible to answer some of these questions by examining how happiness is defined in the literature of psychology by relating them to what happiness means in the workplace if the caveat is added that there are considerable differences between a more general understanding of happiness and specific concerns about the importance of happiness at work.

Fisher (2010a: 25) describes happiness in general as follows: "Happiness is the function of the harmony between the events and conditions in the individual's environment and the established tendencies and behaviors within. This function has the possibility of being reorganized with carefully selected voluntary behaviors" . Aside from rare exceptions, employee happiness within organizations has not been the subject of academic research (Fisher, 2010b). Mostly, these exceptions focused only on job satisfaction. As Fisher (2010a) pointed out that in many of structures have focused on positive attitudes, positive effects and feelings at work, but comprehensive research on happiness at work is still very limited.

As regards the concept of "Happiness at Work", Sousa and Porto (2015) explain "Happiness at work is the frequency of the repetition of the positive emotions (including feelings and moods) perceived by employees in their work life and the pleasure they got from the personal capacity development as they report and from the life goals (self-actualization) they realize" (p. 212). Further studies on "Happiness at work" show the sub-dimensions are as follows: "a) Positive Feelings, b) Negative Feelings and c) Fulfillment" (Paschoal & Tamayo, 2008: 11).

Onay (2011) defines "performance" as "the actions or behaviors that can be measured according to the level of contribution of the employee, and that are in line with the goals of the organization" (p. 4). Two types of employee performance are mentioned in theory and practice. These are a) Task Performance and b) Contextual Performance (Borman and Motowidlo, 1993). Task performance relates to the achievement of basic transformations in the official job description and the realization of their activities. Task performance refers to the basic responsibilities of a job to be fulfilled, and the duties vary from one job to another (Borman and Motowidlo, 1993). Contextual performance, on the other hand, is "the voluntary behaviours that can contribute to all the jobs in the organization and do not need to be included in the job description and have benefits to the social and psychological

environment of the organization” (Motowidlo et al., 1997; Jawahar and Carr., 2007). According to Ashby, Isen, and Turken (1999) a positive mood usually improves employee performance in creative tasks, interpersonal tasks, negotiation tasks, some problem-solving tasks as well as decision-making tasks. A positive mood can have an enhancing effect on task performance (Aspinwall, 1998; Forgas and George 2001; Martin and Clore, 2001). Believing that tasks are performed well or inadequately has significant affects on employees who are concerned about performing well in the workplace (Pekrun and Frese, 1992; Weiss and Cropanzano, 1996).

Fisher (2008) suggests that the simultaneous moods and feelings at work are a strong determinant of perceived performance, which is especially true for employees who care about their job and targets. As Fisher (2010b: 397) reminds us, “Happiness and positive feelings are not created directly by the environment and events, but they arise as a result of people's perception, interpretation and evaluation of these environment and events”.

In earlier studies, Vroom (1964); Iafaldano and Muchinsky (1985) and Judge and Bono (2001) have found a preliminary relationship between job satisfaction and performance at the .18 level. Meta-analytical studies conducted by Judge and Bono, (2001) after correcting reliability and sampling errors, have revealed a medium-strength link between job satisfaction and performance - both in terms of task and contextual. In further studies, correlation with performance increases up to .30 (Judge and Bono, 2001; LePine et al., 2002). Recently, in 2004, it has been found that there is a .55 level link between “job satisfaction” and concurrent “task performance” (Fisher and Noble, 2004, p. 159). Seligman (2002) and Lyubomirsky et al. (2005a) research on the satisfactory aspects of the business environment, focused on Gallup-based survey responses, where improved job satisfaction and results were monitored by managers, and found positive relationships between job satisfaction and job outcomes. Carvalho et al. (2020:19) founded that “The results of the coefficient test line between job satisfaction and employee performance indicate a positive and significant relationship with the coefficient value of 0. 63”.

Happiness and/or subjective well-being have important consequences beyond reflecting the quality of life. According to Lyubomirsky et al. (2005b), numerous studies show that happy individuals do well in various life strata: such as marriage, friendship, income level, job performance and health. These relationships can not only ensure that success brings happiness, but the general development of positive emotions also significantly affect success (Wright and Cropanzano, 2000).

In his book "Work, Happiness and Unhappiness" published in 2007, Warr asks this question: “Why are some people happier or unhappy at work than others?”. According to Warr's “Vitamin Model” (1987, 2007): like vitamins, improvements in work characteristics also improve well-being. They are beneficial until a certain daily dose is exceeded. However, additional amounts taken after this point have a very limited effect on happiness. Another significant source of happiness is good relations with other employees at work.

In “Affective Events Theory”, Weiss and Cropanzano (1996) state that in a stable work order, such relations triggers positive and negative emotions that coincide with emotional events that occur with momentary occurrences.

The “Social Exchange Theory” (Organ, 1977) suggests that happy employees contribute more in the organization and they explain the principles of mutual benefits. Structures such as objective work conditions, job design, personality, psychological climate, job satisfaction, commitment and mood also play a mediator role in performance and organizational citizenship behavior (Judge and Bono, 2001; LePine et al., 2002).

Wright (2002) and his colleagues, who are the pioneers in seeking an answer, “Are happy employees exhibit higher levels of work-related performance behaviors than unhappy employees?” (Wright et al., 2002: 149) concluded that “psychological well-being is positively related with job performance”. Furtherly, the research of Wright, Cropanzano, and Bonett's (2007) provided further explanations for the perennial search for a better understanding of the happy/productive worker thesis. Pioneering research entitled “The moderating role of employee positive well-being in the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance”, revealed by Wright et al (2007: 93), that managers’ “psychological well-being moderates the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance”.

Warr et al. (2014) showed that work performance is principally associated with positive job feelings activation (as cited in Warr and Nielsen, 2018: 5). Findings obtained in all the above studies that examine the theoretical foundations of job satisfaction, performance and happiness variables separately or together differ from one culture to another in the context of motivation and culture.

Therefore, in the following section, the “happy workers are more efficient” hypothesis will be tested through a predicted research model. Fisher, (2010) suggests that factors affecting perceived performance should be investigated through the variable of “happiness at work”. The emphasis of Fisher, along with other pioneering research cited in the literature review, is the main inspiration for this research.

3. Methodology

The research design was made with the survey method based on the sampling of similar respondent quantitatively, and the technique of asking written questions was used as the data collection. The question form used in the research comprises of sections consisting of “job satisfaction”, “happiness at work” and “performance” scales and personal demographic information.

Hofstede's (1980, 1990) understanding of "Work-goals motivation": defines "work-goals as overcoming work, progress, cooperation, family and comfort and security according to the needs and motivational orientations of individuals" (Harpaz, 1990, p. 77; Iguisi 2009, p. 143). According to Hofstede (2001), work goals are an excellent measure of culture as they are shaped by sociological and cultural factors rather than individual psychological differences. Second, the work goals of employees play an active role in the organizational structure in many ways, from conflict resolution to communication, from change to employee motivation. Hofstede compared the findings obtained by analyzing the cultural dimensions on which motivational work goals that affect organizational behavior and practices are based on in different societies and revealed that these differences have strong effects in many management areas from employee motivation to organizational change. Based on this, the research explores whether the role of happiness at work in the effect of job satisfaction on performance would give different results in Italian and Turkish societies in terms of culture.

The research sample is based on the findings of the World Values Survey (WVS), the results of the "World Culture Map" developed by Inglehart-Welzel (2020) and Esmer (2012) and prepared by the "Values Turkey Atlas" while determining the research universe. The research sample was chosen from two countries that appear quite close to each other on the cultural map (Inglehart-Welzel, 2020): Italy, which has high environmental and social tolerance, and represents secular-rational values and Turkey which is generally more collectivistic, traditionally connected to family and authoritarian values, and represents the structure of a national-centric attitude (Hofstede, 1980, Sargut, 2001). Italy (masculine society) which may constitute alternative cultural meanings from Turkey (feminine society) as per subject cross-cultural evaluation. Turkish and Italian societies are known for their historical and geographic proximity beyond the mentioned cultural map of Inglehart-Welzel (2020) are evaluated in two separate clusters and differ from each other as per current cultural dimensions.

Cross-cultural research design, the evaluation, editing, translation and adaptation of the scales to the questionnaire were carried out at the Department of Brain and Behavioral Sciences at Pavia University between February 21 and July 12, 2017. The research sample includes public and private sector employees, health sector members, educators and sales & marketing employees who had been working in the workplace for not less than 6 months. By distributing more than 1500 questionnaires to these groups; 409 valid answers were obtained: 57.9% of participants were educators; 37% sales & marketing employees, and 5.1% healthcare professionals. 85.1% (349 people) of participants were aged 30 and over. The rate of university graduates was 67.9%. 58.2% of the participants have a total seniority of 16 years or more, 44% had been working in the same institution for 16 years or more. In the correspondent sample survey conducted in Turkey, were based in a similar group which consisted of not less than 6 months registration with public and private sector employees, and covered health sector members and educators. 2500 questionnaires were distributed to these groups and 550 valid answers were obtained. The respondent's profile from Turkey was based on mostly public and private sector employees (50.9%) and consists of 19.5% health workers and

educators. 81.9% of the participants are employees over the age of 30 (451 people). The rate of university graduates was 89.5%. The total seniority of 56.2% of the participants was 16 years or more. 26.2% had been working in the same institution for more than 16 years.

Research model and measurement: the model created to discover the relationship between “job satisfaction” and employee perceived “performance” and “happiness at work” can be seen in Figure 2. Sub-dimensions of “job satisfaction” were examined with a dual structure, “intrinsic” and “extrinsic”, accepted as: intrinsic satisfaction: as success, recognition or appreciation, job itself, job responsibility, satisfaction related to the internal quality of the job such as promotion and job change.

Figure 2. Model of Research

Extrinsic satisfaction relates to business policy and management, the method of control, relations with manager and subordinates, working conditions, and compensation of the business environment. “General satisfaction” explains the level of satisfaction and includes both intrinsic and extrinsic dimensions (Weiss et al., 1967).

The sub-dimensions of “happiness at work” are as follows:

1. “Positive feelings” are an indication that events go better than expected and a safe path is followed within the framework of the general origin and function model of the emotion (Carver, 2006). This tendency diverts

personal attention and effort towards other behavioral goals that lead to more needed and unforeseen opportunities. Positive emotions are temporary situations on a personal level such as engagement, liking, pleasure, feeling good, and satisfaction.

2. "Negative feelings" are defined as the functions of the human brain that generate non-standard emotions. Evidence has been demonstrated that mammalian brains are innately built on positive emotions. According to Grinde (2015) people are very happy if their penalty circuits are closed. Activation of negative feeling - especially anxiety, depression, and pain - is a function of the non-standard dimension of well-being.
3. "Fulfillment": "happiness at work" includes the feelings and moods reached in relation to the workplace, as well as complementary actions that add meaningfulness and are aimed at self-expression. Fulfillment dimension assesses the "core elements" of meaningfulness addressed by the eudemonic dimension demonstrated and denominated by Warr (2007) as "self-validation".

"Well-being at work" is a series of actions that accompany positive and/or negative feelings that form the dimensions of the variable and try to reveal how employees behave under the influence of these feelings. Complementary (proving) actions under the influence of feelings are left to the discretion of employees. For example: the statement of "I achieve results that I regard as valuable." aims to measure the effort of the employee to reach the business goals that he/she thinks may be beneficial to the accompaniment of a positive mood.

In the model of the research, "performance" expressions including task performance and contextual performance dimensions developed by Goodman & Svyantek (1999) were used for perceived performance measurement. The "contextual performance" measure can be defined as corporate loyalty behavior towards other employees and citizenship behavior related to the organization. The expressions that make up "task performance" may include, meeting business goals and deadlines, and evaluating the employee incentive and career expectation.

The "Well-being at Work Scale" (WBWS) is a proven and validated scale, which was first described by Paschoal and Tamayo (2008), based on the literature review on workplace happiness has several dimensions. The WBWS has reached its current form used in the literature today after the reliability and validity study was also conducted in the USA (Demo and Paschoal, 2016). As a basic assumption, happiness at work includes emotions and moods gained as well as fulfilment actions in the workplace to realize meaningfulness and self-expression. Thus, the scale is composed of expressions is constituted to include both feelings and accompanying actions to these feelings. The scale indexes psychometric parameters have a high level of reliability and are thus useful for both scientific studies and organizational measurements. This three-factor model is a suitable tool for managers who want to enlighten and improve the workplace happiness of their employees (Demo and Paschoal, 2016). The "Well-being at Work Scale" with 29 expressions was first developed in workplace happiness research by Paschoal and Tamayo (2008) and include in question form, consists of three dimensions of 9 statements of positive

feelings, 12 statements of negative feelings, and 8 statements of fulfillment actions. The “Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale” (Weiss et al., 1967) is used to measure job satisfaction. The Job Satisfaction scale consists of two sub-dimensions, intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction, consist of a total of 20 statements, 12 of which are about intrinsic satisfaction and 8 regarding extrinsic and general satisfaction. For the perceived performance measurement of Goodman & Svyantek (1999), the “Performance” scale has a total of 25 statements. Its sub-dimensions are 16 contextual (altruism and conscientiousness) of 3 reverse and 9 are about the task performance, All the scales in the questionnaire were arranged according to a 5-point Likert scale, and 7 questions for demographic information were included along with 74 statements covering the scales. Both country samples the predicted research model in Figure 2 was used. Correlation and regression analyze were carried out between the variables to measure the direction, quality and effect of the relationships, and the mediation or moderation relationship was examined separately. According to the actual property of findings obtained were tested furtherly with PROCESS (Hayes, 2013), with Jaccard and Turritsi (2003) or AMOS analysis tools.

Findings

In this section, the relationship between the variables determined by considering the findings of analyses conducted in Italy and Turkey will be evaluated. The scales have been implemented in Italian and Turkish with cross-checks provided by experts. The valid forms of 409 each obtained from the Italian sample were subjected to factor analysis to test the validity and reliability of the scales. KMO values regarding the suitability of the data set were examined: job satisfaction; KMO value 0.905 $p = .000$; gathered under two factors, as intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction, happiness at work; KMO value 0.946 $p = .000$; expressions are divided into three dimensions as expected. Performance; KMO value 0.874 $p = .000$; statements are among the two dimensions of the performance scale; divided into contextual and task performance. Cronbach Alfa value is the coefficient and being over 0.70 indicates the reliability of the data set. The factor explanation of all dimensions is 53.24% of the total variance of the sample. To reveal the quality and quantity of the relationship between the variables, correlation and regression analyses were performed between them. The findings of Italy sample were retested with the PROCESS method (Hayes, 2013). Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationships between variables. As per findings in Table 1: the “job satisfaction” has a positive relationship to the “happiness at work” at $p < .001$ level. It is also seen that “job satisfaction” has a significant relationship with the “performance” variable positively at $p < .001$ level, while job satisfaction has a significant positive relationship with “performance”. “Job satisfaction” establishes the highest (0.701) relationship with “happiness at work”, while it has the lowest (0.164) relationship with “performance”. Also, there is a significant relationship between “happiness at work” and the “performance” variable at 0.328 at $p < .001$ level.

Regression analyses were conducted to explore the role of “happiness at work” in the relationship between “job satisfaction” and “performance” to find out the nature of correlation. Analyses were revealed that “happiness at work” has no moderation effect in the relationship between “job satisfaction” and “performance”. Therefore, mediation has searched for with regression analysis. Durbin-Watson value below 2, shows that there was no autocorrelation were exist and VIF value is around 1, indicates that there was no multi-linearity and the model was significant as a whole as per Anova table. Mediating variable is defined as a variable that eliminates or decreases the strength of an observed relationship between independent and dependent variables due to its different tie with variables (Baron and Kenny, 1986). Further analyses were made by using Baron and Kenny steps to determine whether “happiness at work” is in a meaningful relationship as the mediator variable and if so, how and to what extent it causes mediating relationship among the other variables. In the analysis made with Baron and Kenny method, several regression steps pursued to examine the relationship 1) between “job satisfaction” and “happiness at work”, 2) the relationship between “job satisfaction” and “performance”, 3) the relationship “happiness at work” with “performance”, 4) finally the relationship of “happiness at work” together with “job satisfaction” with “performance” as shown in Table 2. As it is seen that “job satisfaction” explains happiness at work in the first model. (Beta coefficient = .701). In the second model, Anova table is significant at $p < .000$ level, Beta value is .164 and R2 change = .027, and job satisfaction explains performance. In the third model, the relationship between the “happiness at work” and “performance” is significant with 0.328 at the level of $p < .001$, and the regression value is at R2 change = .108 at $p < .000$ (see Table 2). In the fourth model, “job satisfaction” by adding the “happiness at work” variable to test whether is it a mediator variable or not. According to Anova the model is still significant at $p < .000$, but the effect of the “job satisfaction” variable is changed to $p = .048$ level and the relationship between “job satisfaction “and “performance changed into the negative direction.

Table 1. Italian Sample Correlation Analysis of Variables and Dimensions

Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. Job satisfaction	409	3,38	0.673	-										
2. Happiness at work	409	3,46	0.604	.701**	-									
3. Performance	409	3,98	0.472	.164**	.328**	-								
4. Introvert satisfaction	409	3,83	0.657	-	-	-	-							
5. Extrovert satisfaction	409	2,93	0.876	-	-	-	.534**	-						
6. General satisfaction	409	-	-	-	-	-	.444**	.702**	-					
7. Negative feelings	409	3,39	0.565	-	-	-	.405**	.398**	.356**	-				
8. Positive feelings	409	3,31	0.790	-	-	-	.603**	.592**	.480**	.558**	-			
9. Fulfilment	409	3,68	0.778	-	-	-	.644**	.455**	.339**	.405**	.715**	-		
10. Contextual performance	409	4,05	0.516	-	-	-	.202**	.035**	.046**	.133**	.190**	.283**	-	
11. Task performance	409	3,90	0.556	-	-	-	.273**	.050**	.060**	.189**	.243**	.384**	.554**	-

***p* < .01.

*“M” of the “Happiness at work” variable has been obtained by getting reverse the dimension of “Negative feelings” item.

Source: Authors’ calculations

If the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable is weakened or the effect of the independent variable has abolished, the variable in the model is mediator variable (Baron and Kenny, 1986). After the mediation test based on regression analysis, path analysis was performed with PROCESS (Hayes, 2013) method and the mediation test was repeated to both obtain proof and determine the nature and dimensions of the relationship.

Table 2. Regression Findings of Italian Sample

Model		β	Std. Error	Beta	t	P
1	(Constant) ^a	1.334	.110		12.183	.000
	Job Satisfaction	.629	.032	.701	19.812	.000

a. Dependent variable: Happiness at work

Model		β	Std. Error	Beta	t	P
2	(Constant) ^b	3.594	.118		30.335	.000
	Job Satisfaction	.115	.034	.164	3.353	.001

b. Dependent Variable: Performance

Model		β	Std. Error	Beta	t	P
3	(Constant) ^c	3.095	.129		23.902	.000
	Happiness at Work	.257	.037	.328	7.012	.000
4	(Constant) ^c	3.157	.132		16.452	.000
	Happiness at Work	.328	.051	.419	6.412	.000
	Job Satisfaction	-.091	.046	-.130	-1.985	.048

c. Dependent Variable: Performance

	R	R2	R2 Change	F	p
Model 1	.701	.490	.491	392.501	.000
Model 2	.164	.024	.027	11.245	.001
Model 3	.328	.106	.108	49.175	.000
Model 4	.341	.112	.009	3.941	.048

* $p < .05$. *** $p < .001$.

Source: Authors' calculations

In the path analysis showing the coefficients, there is a significant relationship between “job satisfaction” and “happiness at work” ($p < .001$); the path coefficient is $A = .63$; “job satisfaction’s path coefficient resulting from “happiness at work” through “performance” is $C = .33$ and $C' = .12$ ($p < .001$); but the path coefficient between “job satisfaction” and “performance” is $B = -.09$ and it is significant at $p < .05$ level ($p = .0478$).

Figure 3. Path Coefficiencies of Italian Sample

Source: Authors' calculation

The path coefficients are in Figure 3 and see their total direct and indirect effects are in Table 3. No zero (0) value took place between the bootstrapped a and b values at lower and upper level confidence (95%) range (.1355 and .2839) at the “Completely Standardized Indirect Effect of Job Satisfaction on Performance” (see Table 3). Lack of zero value (0) between the bootstrapped values (in lower and upper confidence intervals) proves the mediating effect of happiness at work variable. Consequently “job satisfaction” has a statistically significant if indirect relationship with “performance” through “happiness at work” as seen in Table 3, (Preacher and Kelly , 2011). “Happiness at work” has a full mediating effect in the relationship between job satisfaction and performance. Because, when the "happiness at work" variable is included in the model, the direct effect of “job satisfaction” on “performance” loses its former function (see Table 2, Model 4). Therefore, “job satisfaction” can explain “performance” only with the positive contribution of “happiness at work”. In sum, the correlation and regression analysis resulted that "happiness at work" has a positive reinforcing effect and “job satisfaction” significantly improves employee “performance” through “happiness at work”.

Table 3. Italian Sample Total, Direct and Indirect Effects of Variables

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% CI		p
			LL	UL	
Total Effect(s) of Job Satisfaction on Performance	.1151	.0343	.0476	.1826	.0009
Direct Effect(s) of Job Satisfaction on Performance	-.0911	.0459	-.1813	-.0009	.0478
Effect ^a	Estimate	BootSE	95% LL	CI UL	p

Indirect Effect(s) of Job Satisfaction on Performance	Happiness at work	.2062	.0378	.1355	.2839	.0000
Partially Standardized Indirect Effect(s) of Job Satisfaction on Performance	Happiness at work	.4362	.0750	.2929	.5882	.0000
Completely Standardized Indirect Effect(s) of Job Satisfaction on Performance	Happiness at work	.2938 ^a	.0505	.1953 ^b	.3938 ^c	.0000

a. Happiness at work (Mediator effect)

b. Happ. at work mediation effect (LL)

c. Happ. at work mediation effect (UL)

* $p < .05$. *** $p < .001$.

Source: Authors' calculation

A similar study was conducted with the Turkish sample. The validity and reliability of the scales examined on data set with 550 valid forms. The Job satisfaction: KMO value was found as 0.915 ($p = .000$). The expressions are grouped under two factors: intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. It was determined in the factor analysis that the two statements did not constitute a separate dimension of "general satisfaction" because their Cronbach Alpha values were low (0.397). These statements were excluded in the subsequent analyzes, and 18 statements of 20 were evaluated. KMO value of "happiness at work" is 0.968 ($p = .000$). Overall statements were divided into three dimensions as predicted in the original scale.

"Performance" KMO value was found to be 0.921 ($p = .000$). The expressions were collected in 2 dimensions: task and contextual (consentiousness and altruism). The explanatory factor of all dimensions was 56.69% of the total variance.

Correlation analysis of the dimensions of the variables was made as seen in Table 4. "Contextual" and "task performance", "intrinsic" and "extrinsic satisfaction" of job satisfaction, "positive" and "negative feelings" and "fulfillment" of happiness at work, are in a positive and meaningful relationship with each other. The "general satisfaction" with a low Cronbach Alpha value as per factor analysis was not included in the correlation test the lowest correlation (.138) is between "contextual performance" and "task performance". Following the correlation findings, regression analysis was conducted to explore the role of "happiness at work" in the relationship between "job satisfaction" and "performance", to examine their relational nature. Analyses in Turkish sample have concluded there is no mediating effect of happiness at work variable in the relationship between "job satisfaction" and "performance".

Table 4. Turkish Sample Correlation Analysis of Variables and Dimensions

Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Job Satisfaction	550	3,45	0,74	-									
2. Happiness at work*	550	3,37	0,87	,713**	-								
3. Performance	550	4,02	0,53	,390**	,331**	-							
4. Introvert satisfaction	550	3,78	0,69	-	-	-	-						
5. Extrovert satisfaction	550	3,11	0,92	-	-	-	,673**	-					
6. Negative feelings	550	3,35	1,15	-	-	-	,412**	,577**	-				
7. Positive feelings	550	3,11	0,99	-	-	-	,584**	,670**	,696**	-			
8. Fulfilment	550	3,67	0,82	-	-	-	,660**	,506**	,397**	,618**	-		
9. Contextual performance	550	3,97	0,52	-	-	-	,418**	,258**	,158**	,262**	,462**	-	
10. Task performance	550	4,07	0,64	-	-	-	,452**	,263**	,138**	,276**	,554**	,730**	-

***p* < .01.

*“M” of the “Happiness at work” variable has been obtained by getting reverse the dimension of “Negative feelings” items.

Source: Authors’ calculations

Therefore, moderation has tested with regression analysis. In the hierarchical regression analysis (see Table 5) conducted to question the effect of the moderator variable, the changes in R2 at each stage were observed. In the first model, it is seen that “job satisfaction” predicts “performance”. (Beta coefficient = .390). In the second model, “job satisfaction” and “happiness at work” together in the relationship with “performance and job satisfaction” explains “performance”. In the third model, to determine the nature of the moderator effect, “job satisfaction” and “happiness at work” variables with the interaction variable (predictor variable multiplied by moderator variable) obtained from their centered product were each by each included in regression and tested all together with “performance” variable.

Table 5. Regression Findings of Turkish Sample

Model	β	Std.Error	Beta	t	p
1 (Constant) ^a	3.047	.099		30.635	.000
Job Satisfaction	.279	.028	.390	9.909	.000
2 (Constant) ^a	3.017	.101		30.018	.000
Job Satisfaction	.224	.040	.313	5.594	.000
Happiness at work	.065	.034	.107	1.918	.056
3 (Constant) ^a	2.944	.104		28.244	.000
Job Satisfaction	.228	.040	.318	5.698	.000
Happiness at Work	.074	.034	.122	2.175	.030
Interaction	.044	.018	.098	2.466	.014

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

	R	R2	R2 Change	F	p
Model 1	.390	.150	.152	98.188	.000
Model 2	.397	.155	.006	3.678	.056
Model 3	.409	.162	.009	6.082	.014

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

Source: Authors' calculations

The Beta value in the relationship of “job satisfaction” with “performance” (the outcome variable), is significant at $p < .001$ with $\beta = .318$ (see Table 5, Model 3). In the next step, the beta value of the happiness at work variable with the interaction value included in the analysis increased to .122 and made it statistically significant ($p = .030$). If the moderator variable (happiness at work) has a statistically significant relationship with the independent variable (job satisfaction), on the other hand, the moderator variable does not predict the outcome variable (performance) as an independent variable, the variable in the model is considered to have a full moderator effect (Sharma et al, 1981). Although in these findings - in order to verify the statistically significant change in R2 with the inclusion of the interaction variable in the model - it is necessary to examine three separate regression lines created by giving the average value to the moderator variable with the mean value of one unit below standard deviation and one unit above standard deviation on the graph to determine that the lines are not parallel (Jaccard and Turrisi, 2003). Unparallel lines are shown at Figure 4.

Figure 4. The Graphic of Job satisfaction on Performance Through Happiness at Work

Source: Authors calculation with the assistance of program created by Jose, P. E., 2013, www.victoria.ac.nz/psyc/about/staff/paul-jose, 31.01.2019

The moderation test was repeated with AMOS to both ensure and determine the dimensions of the relationship. Related within the framework of the model, the independent variable (job satisfaction) and moderator variable (happiness at work) were standardized by taking their average values, then the variables and moderating effect were observed with path analysis of AMOS (Figure 5). The standardized independent variable, moderator variable and interact variable (centered predictor variable X centered moderator variable) have a significant and positive relationship with the performance as shown as in Table 6.

Figure 5. Path Analysis of Turkish Sample

ZHpW = Happiness at Work, ZJSat = Job Satisfaction, ZPerf = Performance

Int =Interaction

Source: Authors' calculations

The effect of the standardized “happiness at work” variable is .12 ($p = .029$), the standardized “job satisfaction” variable .32 ($p = .000$) and the interaction” of happiness at work and job satisfaction .084 ($p = .013$) on “performance”. Besides, as seen in the critical ratio (C.R.) column of Figure 5, the fact that the values obtained by dividing the standard error by the covariance are above 1.96 for each variable confirms that the results obtained are statistically significant and valid.

Table 6. AMOS Moderation Analysis: Regression Weights of Turkish Sample

Effect		Estimate	SE	C.R.	p
Zperf	← ZJSat	.318	.056	5.714	***
ZPerf	← ZHpW	.122	.056	2.181	.029
ZPerf	← Interaction	.084	.034	2.473	.013

Zperf = Performance, ZJSat = Job satisfaction, ZHpW = Happiness at work
C.R. = Critical Ratio

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

The findings confirm that “happiness at work” plays a moderator role in the effect of “job satisfaction” on “performance”. When compared with the proposed research model, both analysis finding supports the model shown in Figure 6.

The study shows that the models found in both analyses are in comply with proposed model that constitutes the basic hypothesis, although different effects were obtained in each research. According to the model found in the Italian sample (see Figure 6), the movement of action works through the happiness at work variable shows that the Italian findings comply with the full mediating role through the proposed research model. In the model of the Turkish sample, the “happiness at work” variable act as a relationship between “job satisfaction” and “performance” as the moderator variable.

Figure 6. Comparison of the Proposed Model and Research Finding Models

Discussions

As per comparison of both research samples: Italy is 409 and Turkey 550; women's participation was 65% in Italy, and 46% in Turkey. The age groups in both countries are similar, but there were more participants over 50 in Italy. The educational background in both surveys is also alike, as the proportion of participants with higher education and postgraduate education constitutes most of all participants in both countries. The distribution of occupational groups is slightly different: in the Italian sample educators were in the majority with 49%, whereas in the Turkish sample private sector and public employees constituted 47%. In a comparative analysis, in the model of Italy, the “happiness at work” variable creates a stronger link than the direct link between “job satisfaction” and “performance” (see Table 7). According to this model, the fact that the dynamics of action works through the “happiness at work” variable indicates that the Italian findings are compatible with the full mediating role as per the proposed research model. “Job satisfaction” indirectly affects “performance” through happiness at work at .29 level ($p < .001$) and plays fully mediating role. If the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variables is removed, this demonstrates a full mediating relationship (Baron and Kenny, 1986).

Table 7. Comparison of Findings Between Italian and Turkish Sample

Research Model	Indirect Effect	Interaction	Findings
Italian sample	.12***	–	Full Mediation
Turkish sample	–	.084***	Full Moderation

*** $p < .001$.

In the Turkish sample, “happiness at work” has a moderator effect between “job satisfaction” and “performance”. The moderator effect can be seen in the relationships between dependent and independent variables when the variable is weak, mediocre, and high. If the moderating variable is weak, mediocre, and high, it reflects the power of relationships between the independent and dependent variables as weak or mediocre or high. For example: “job satisfaction” is reflected most when “happiness at work” is high in “performance” even if job satisfaction directly predicts “performance”. Therefore, when happiness is considered, it plays a role that strengthens the effect on “performance”. “Job satisfaction” has a full moderating effect on “performance” with the interaction of “happiness at work” with a .08 level ($p < .001$).

We predicted that the effect of known motivation theories might be changed by cultural differences while creating our model, which explores the problematic of the “Role of employee happiness between job satisfaction and performance”. Please see the citation we have put forward the reference of Harpaz (1990) and

Iguisi (2009) to Hofstede's motivation studies. In this context, we compared the cultural dimensions of Italy and Turkey which are discussed in different studies in the fictional research model, with the validated models of both sides and their similarities and divergences. These studies are Hofstede's advanced work (1980, 1990, 2011), GLOBE (2019) and World Values Survey (WVS) (Inglehart and Welzel, 2020) analyzing Italy and Turkey in terms of cultural dimensions shown as on Table 8, compiled by the authors.

When Italy and Turkey are compared in terms of similar and different aspects of cultural dimensions; *Power Distance*, *Individualistic / Collectivistic* dimensions are similar in both Hofstede (1990) and GLOBE (2019). However, WVS (2020) is separated as *Secular-Rational and Traditional*. While Hofstede's cultural codes were separated as *Masculinity / Femininity*, *Gender Egalitarianism* was found to be the same for both samples in GLOBE (2019) research. In the *Long-term Orientation* trend, Hofstede (1990, 2011) samples differ (Italy is high, Turkey is low), while GLOBE (2019) is similar for both countries. In the dimension of *Indulgence*, both samples had different values in Hofstede (1990), but GLOBE (2019) determined the *Performance Orientation* as the same. The examples of Italy and Turkey, which have a high value in the *Uncertainty Avoidance* dimension, are similar, but GLOBE qualifies Italy as medium and Turkey as partial low.

“Hofstede’s work has come to dominate the literature, partly because he was the first to develop a parsimonious national culture framework consisting of multiple cultural dimensions and also because he provided country measures (indexes) on these dimensions” (Beugelsdijk et al., 2017: 31). According to Hofstede (1990, 2011), both countries differ significantly in terms of cultural values (Table 8). The most important of these are *Power Distance*, *Individualism / Collectivism*, *Long Term Orientation*, *Masculinity / Femininity*, *Indulgence*. Only *Uncertainty Avoidance*, Italy and Turkey are in the similar value group with high degree. Hierarchical structuring of power and authority from top to bottom rather than a horizontal distribution among individuals in the society shows that the perception of the distance of power in both communities is similar (Hofstede 1980, Sargut, 2001). As can be seen in the Table 8, there are more divergent aspects. While Italian society strives to secure itself as much as possible

Table 8. Comparison of Cultural Dimensions Between Italy and Turkey

	Hofstede	GLOBE	WVS (World Value Survey)
	<i>Power Distance</i>	<i>Power Distance</i>	
Italy	Low	Low	-
Turkey	High	High	-
	<i>Individualism/Collectivism</i>	<i>Individualism/Collectivism</i>	<i>Traditional / Secular-Rational</i>

Italy	Individualistic	Individualist	Secular-Rational
Turkey	Collectivistic	Medium	Traditional
<i>Masculinity/ Femininity</i>		<i>Gender Egalitarianism</i>	
Italy	Masculine	Medium	-
Turkey	Feminine	Medium	-
<i>LongTerm Orientation</i>		<i>Future Orientation</i>	<i>Self Expression/Survival</i>
Italy	High	Medium	Self Expressionist
Turkey	Low	Medium	Survival
<i>Indulgence</i>		<i>Performance Orientation</i>	-
Italy	Low	Medium	-
Turkey	High	Medium	-
<i>In Group Collectivism</i>			
Italy	-	High	-
Turkey	-	High	-
<i>Uncertainty Avoidance</i>		<i>Uncertainty Avoidance</i>	
Italy	High	Medium	-
Turkey	High	Partially Low	-
<i>Assertiveness</i>			
Italy	-	Medium	-
Turkey	-	Medium High	-

Source: Authors' review and compilations.

and prevent ambiguity in situations where uncertainty prevails, values such as power, success, achievement, fame, change, growth, and promotion are preferred. In this respect, the situation is not different in Turkey - though, feminine factors should not be totally set aside - and point to a line close to the break-off. Collectivism, the characteristics of belonging to the family and other social groups come to the fore in social relations. In business relations, traditional ties such as friendship, acquaintance, kinship rather than social security, as well as respect for parents, tolerance and personal protection are widely observed in Turkish society (Sargut, 2001). There are also diverging and similar aspects in the other studies mentioned (GLOBE, WVS). Therefore, the fact that the research findings are different in the two samples (Italy mediation, Turkey moderation) makes us think that the performance variable based on the happiness of job satisfaction could be

affected by cultural differences. Thus, we wanted to discuss this issue in terms of its contribution to the field.

Consequently, evaluation of the above cultural dimensions verifies different results for each study. The participants in the Italian sample are influenced by their feelings of "happiness at work" in expressing themselves better. In the Turkish sample, while "job satisfaction" and employee "performance" are in a direct and significant relationship, the factor of "happiness at work" is not enough to strengthen the relationship on its own. While "happiness at work" shows a moderator effect through "job satisfaction" and plays a regulatory role in Turkish, employee "job satisfaction" in the Italian sample is not directly explained by "performance". In other words, when happiness is included in the work, "job satisfaction" is insufficient to predict "performance" on its own. As Fisher (2010) has illustrated, it needs the mediation of other factors. There was, however, a direct relationship between employee "performance" and "job satisfaction" in the Turkish sample. If employees are happy in their job, their job satisfaction reflects more on his/her performance.

"Happiness at work" appears to display a relatively high impact in Italy ($r = .29$), whereas its mediating impact ($r = 0.84$) is considerably lower in Turkey. The aim of such comparisons is to make a scientific contribution to the debate based on research findings that takes into consideration previous studies that suggest that cultural differences can affect the findings from one society to another. For example, in previous studies based on power distance, individualism, uncertainty avoidance, masculinity / femininity and orientation, Hofstede (1993), "has found that there are large differences in motivation factors between Chinese and western workers" (as cited in Fisher and Yuan, 1998, p. 516). Veenhoven (2012) stressed that "happiness can differ across cultures. If happiness depends on meeting local standards of the good life, it can be high in cultures where these standards can be easily met and low where the meeting of these standards is out of reach of most people" (p. 12). However, as per research on "The Happy-Productive Worker Model" with Spanish workers conducted by Peiró et al. (2019) resulted that "there are antagonistic patterns of happiness and performance (i.e., happy-unproductive, and in some cases, unhappy-productive" (p.7).

Although it can be accepted that there will be a certain margin of error in this study, the fact that all discussions, evaluations and interpretation are firmly established on a scientific basis and thus depends on fact; it might, however, be challenged by new cross-sectional and longitudinal studies in various societies.

4. Conclusions

Since the Hawthorne Studies, the effects of employee attitudes on productivity and performance have been widely discussed, and "Are happy employees more efficient?" remains a fundamental question on the agenda. Moccia (2016) stated that "The new millennium goal is to be happy at work. Happiness at

work is presented as an issue of utmost importance” (p.144). Although the relationship between job satisfaction and performance has been the subject of research for many years, results are still contestable as in the literature review demonstrates. Fisher (2010a) stresses on that factors such as job satisfaction, which affects performance, should be considered together with other variables to maintain their importance in terms of “happiness at work”. However, discussion would be enriched by further research focusing on the "happiness at work" phenomenon as Fisher (2010a) emphasizes. In this study, the role of "happiness at work" in the relationship between "job satisfaction" and "performance" was questionable, unlike results based in Italy and Turkey.

The research form used in the survey consists of “job satisfaction”, “happiness at work” and “performance” scales and personal demographic information. The research sample was chosen from Italy and Turkey took place on the cultural map of Ingelhart-Welzel (2020). The research sample includes public and private sector employees, health personnel, educators, and industry workers. The data obtained from both samples were examined with statistical data analysis methods and the findings were compared by the characteristics of the population favourably.

According to the findings, job satisfaction of employees in the Italian sample explains through the happiness they experience at work, mediates their performance. However, in Turkey, while there is a direct relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance, the moderator effect of happiness at work comes to the fore. In other words, if the employee is happy in his job, job satisfaction is more reflected in his performance.

The study contributes to interactional research by bringing the "happy worker" debate into the workplace setting where high person-organization interaction occurs. Findings provided substantial support for happiness at work as a predictor of organizational outcomes, but limited and mixed results for the role of calculated fit. Results of the study overall indicate that an organization and person fit were significantly influenced by culture, by job satisfaction as predictors of employee performance through happiness at work. It significantly supports Hofstede’s assumption that motivational work goals that affect organizational behavior and practices in different societies cause different results with cultural dimensions and have strong effects in many management areas from employee motivation to organizational change. The study also makes a new contribution to the field of organizational behaviors, as cross-cultural research to the findings that Herzberg (2003) has tested the effect of the two-factor (Motivation and Hygiene) on job satisfaction in six countries of different cultures.

Considering that employees spend most of their lives at work, the relationship between job satisfaction and happiness is of great importance. Organizational behavior aims to improve employee satisfaction and outcome variables at the individual, group, and organization levels. In contemporary societies, we observe that the necessity of removing the protective elements from the working conditions and directing them to the motivating elements has become a part of the functioning of the organization. Therefore, this article explains the triggering mechanisms of employee motivation with its original findings and provides important clues to organizational managers and prospective researchers. Except for rare studies,

employee happiness has not been the subject of academic research until the last two decades. Since comprehensive studies on “happiness at work” have been limited as encountered, current findings bring an opportunity for a fresh review and/or an elaboration on past research. One of the other implications is that it may constitute benefits for intercultural human resources management. Thus, “well-being” or in another word “happiness” in the workplace will resonate more as an indispensable phenomenon for proper and competitive organizational functioning.

There are several limitations to this study. First, this research is limited to cultural environments at a specific time and a limited sample of societies. A second limitation is the use of a relatively homogenous sample and the restricted quantity of responders. Another significant limitation is that findings are shaped by responses in a questionnaire form, as well as the perception capacities of responding subjects, and their self-evaluation competence. In this sense, the perspective within the scope of the research on the relations between the person and the organization must be in the direction of the perceptions of the employees about their jobs. To reach a clear generalization, the number of samples can be further increased in subsequent studies, different methods can be adopted, longitudinal studies can be made in time and space, but the fact that this research, like the others, is within the scope of objective evaluation and error of contemporary statistical methods should be considered.

Even considering these limitations, this research should serve as an example of a research model for future studies of the “happiness at work” structure and thus enabling further evaluations of cross-cultural comparisons. Nevertheless, this study is limited to a consideration of Italy and Turkey: subsequent research is thus needed with further cross-cultural studies of the “happiness at work” structure to provide testing problematic with various samples. Also, the research model can be pioneering as it will make possible further evaluations and comparisons of cross-cultural differences in the field of organizational behavior. The importance is that it explores the role of happiness in a western culture where the scale of “happiness at work” developed and compares the results with findings of research with local studies. Therefore, contributes to a basis for the evaluation of cultural differences in that context. It is thought that the "happiness at work" approach has been brought to the agenda by examining the problem of "job satisfaction" and "performance", which sheds light on the theories mentioned in the field of positive organizational behavior. The findings provide evidence for the assumption that "Happy employees are more productive at work" and contribute to previous studies, suggesting that cultural dimensions also may affect behavioral person-organization relations.

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